

Bio-inspired design of tactile sensors based on ionic polymer metal composites

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SUMMARY

Ionic polymer metal composites (IPMC) have been widely investigated as newly-emerging materials for transducer applications due to their good performance, such as low weight, good flexibility and large strain. A bio-inspired design was described and applied to build 3-D papillae dome structure for vectorial tactile sensors.

Keywords: IPMC, Flemion, bio-inspired, tactile sensor, array

INTRODUCTION

The electrical-chemical-mechanical effect in ionic polymer metal composites (IPMCs) was first reported by Oguro et al in 1992 [1]. A typical IPMC sample contains an ionic polymeric membrane saturated with solvent (usually water) and counter ions, which is sandwiched by two compliant metal electrodes. Ionic polymer metal composite have already attracted great attention as a recently developed new material for actuator and sensor applications due to its potential as a bio-mimetic candidate. It is physically light and flexible. Moreover, it could be easily actuated under a really low voltage [2, 3]. Conversely, we demonstrated that it was able to sense small deformation or force as sensor [4]. IPMC is a promising candidate for bio-related applications mainly due to its biocompatibility, flexible structures and operation in wet condition [5].

Due to the similarities in the mechanism of electroactive polymer and some biological actuation and sensing systems, we can learn about their energy-conservative sensing and actuation mechanisms as well as the relationship between microstructure and macro-behavior for these intelligent materials [6, 7]. Biological systems are an ideal intelligent structural system with integrated sensing and actuating capability.

In Fig.1, the natural mechanosensor of papillae in cucurbitaceae possesses well-developed sensor microstructure and its distributed pattern on the surface is a very good scheme of arrayed mechanosensor system for identification of vectorial forces. Most of the tactile sensors that have been developed so far are based on piezoelectric sensing elements covered by elastomeric top coating or by piezo-resistive mechanism. To extend the sensing capability of tactile sensors in x-y-z three directions, novel design of three dimensional structures based on flexible materials should be achieved.

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrograph of ventral side of tendril showing a trichome and numerous tactile papillae. X 390 [8].

The knowledge gained from the mechanisms of the biological species is key input for designing intelligent materials and systems. By studying these biological systems, we are attempting to design arrayed tactile sensor system with extruded dome structure, which can detect external mechanical stimuli in x-y-z directions. In this paper, we will briefly discuss about voltage response given by this prototype tactile sensor element. Inspired by this natural tactile sensor design, we attempt to design arrayed tactile sensor system and will report the preliminary results of a single tactile sensor in this paper. Fig.2 shows an illustrative sketch of ionic polymer metal composite (IPMC) sensing mechanism.

Fig.2 Illustrative sketch for Ionic Polymer Metal Composite (IPMC) sensing mechanism: (a) undeformed and (b) right after sudden deformation

In non-deformed state, Fig.2(a), cations inside the membrane are uniformly distributed in the ionomer network and no signal will be detected in this equilibrium state. When force (or displacement) is applied to IPMC sensor, a non-uniform distribution of cations will be induced, which is shown in the deformed state in Fig.2(b), resulting in the surface charge accumulating on the electrode to balance the local surplus cations or ionomeric anions. This surface accumulated charge can be easily detected by a data acquisition device. As in biological sensing units, no electric power is required for idle state and sensing time course.

Previously, we reported that Flemion based IPMC tactile sensor with 3-dimensional dome structure was able to detect forces in x-y-z multi-directions [9]. In this paper, sensing signals of voltage will be discussed based on the sample with dispensed surface circuit electrode. Particularly, we will compare the sensing signal characteristics of Flemion IPMC sensor from our previous work [10].

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of IPMC based on Flemion

Deposition of gold electrode is done according to the impregnation-reduction technique following a recipe developed by Fujiwara et al [11] and further improved by Le Guilly et al [12]. In this technique, a gold complex $[\text{Au}(\text{Phen})\text{Cl}_2]^+$ is introduced into the Flemion membrane with K^+ as counter ions by ion exchange. This process will fully take place if the amount of gold complex in the exchange solution is sufficient to drive the exchange and if the affinity of the membrane for its present cation is not too high. Then, Flemion membrane with gold complex is soaked in de-ionized water for reduction. Small amount of 5wt% sodium sulfite solution are gradually added to reducing bath and the temperature is carefully controlled for slowly ramp. For thin Flemion membrane, the reduction process will finish after six hours, followed by rinsing in acid and de-ionized water for cleaning. Finally, all the samples were immersed in KOH solution with 1mol/L for ion exchange. The resultant samples were Flemion based IPMC with K^+ as counter ion.

Preparation of 3 by 3 Flemion based IPMC tactile sensor arrays with dispensed surface circuit

To achieve surface electrode for signal in/out circuit, dispensing system was applied and the results were compared. The final goal is to obtain highly conductive circuit line with good attachment to substrate surface.

All the experiments using ink dispensing system were done at Prof. Kimura's lab at Shinshu University, Ueda campus, Japan. Several solutions were prepared for dispensing purpose, see Table 1. All the solutions were mixed and sonicated for 30mins, then magnetic-stirred for additional 30mins.

Table 1 Conductive Solution for Dispensing System

Sol #	Pt/C	Nafion sol	methanol	ethanol	Silver colloid	Dotite D-550	Dotite P-255
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(a)	16.8mg	127.63 μ l	1ml				
(b)	16.8mg	127.63 μ l		1ml			
(c)		0.5ml			0.5ml		
(d)		0.5ml				0.5ml	
(e)							1ml

Fig. 3 Dispensing System used for surface circuit line drawing

Shot mini SL Dispensing System by Musashi Engineering Inc. was used for this study as shown in Fig.3. Syringe was cleaned before using via sonication bath, and then solution was loaded. Depending on the line width of desired pattern as well as solution viscosity, different needles were adapted. The pressure could be tuned according to different solution viscosity and the substrate membrane was placed on the movable platform controlled by PC. The height of the needle as well as needle moving speed was controlled by system control panel.

(a)

(b)

Fig.4 Surface circuit lines: (a) design and (b) Flemion IPMC with dispensed circuit lines

The design of the surface circuit line was shown in Fig.4, which was based on a three by three dome array. Each dome has four domains, which needs one pair of electrode for each of them. The red lines in Fig.4(a) represent the laser cut patterns previously done at Washington Technology Center; the dark lines denote the dispensed lines. As the conductive solution contains epoxy resin, one side of the patterns was finished first, and then the sample with dispensed lines was heated at 120 °C for 30min for epoxy resin curing process. After that, the other side of the patterns was done using the same approach. The finished sample was immersed in deionized water overnight and shown in Fig.4(b). No peeling-off of lines was observed, suggesting good attachment between conductive lines and IPMC surface. However, we observed surface warp after lines applied, indicating surface stress had been introduced. Further investigation is needed to reduce surface stress and improve IPMC flatness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of dispensed surface circuit

a) Optical microscope photos

Fig. 5 Optical microscope photos of dispensed silver lines on Flemion IPMC substrate

Optical microscope photos of dispensed silver lines on Flemion IPMC surface are shown in Fig.5. It demonstrates that continuous silver line was successfully made by dispensing system. All of them show reasonably good adhesion to the surface with small contact angle. No cracks were found in either straight lines or the elbow.

Fig.6 shows the photos for circuit lines based on solution (a) and (c) in Table 1. For solution containing Pt on carbon black, some cracks with red circle highlight were observed. Isolated aggregation was found based on solution containing Nafion solution mixed with silver colloid, indicating that high resistance might occur in this case.

(a) (b)
 Fig. 6 Optical microscope photos for surface circuit lines on Flemion IPMC with solutions containing (a) Pt/C and (b) silver colloid

b) Line height test

Fig.7 Line height determined by profilometer

The height of the line was determined by *profilometer Surfcoorder ET-4000* (Kosaka Laboratory, Japan). Several spots were selected for the measurements (see Fig.7), most of them were within 53-60μm, suggesting good uniformity could be obtained. However,

some parts were 20 μ m lower than average, and the solution might need further improvement for uniform distribution.

c) Resistance test

The setup for two-probe resistance measurement is connected to Keithley 2612 System SourceMeter. For all the measurements, the distance between two probes was carefully maintained at 2mm. The resistance of samples with different solutions is listed in Table 2. The solution numbers are corresponding to the ones in Table 1. Samples based on solution #(a), #(b) and #(c) shows large average resistance, which could be explained by photos in Fig.6. The sample based on solution containing Pt/C appeared to have cracks on surface, while sample based on Nafion/Silver colloid solution has aggregated ‘islands’ rather than uniformed lines. It clearly shows that the sample with only epoxy-based silver paste has the lowest resistance, indicating excellent conductivity could be achieved by this solution.

Table 2 Resistance of samples with different solutions

Sol #	1(Ω)	2(Ω)	3(Ω)	Average(Ω)
(a)	~440	~520	~490	~483
(b)	~350	~290	~540	~393
(c)	~980	~1300	~1000	~1093
(d)	~22	~43	~39	~35
(e)	1.4	2.1	1.9	~1.8

Characterization of Flemion based IPMC tactile sensor with dispensed surface circuit

One dome of 3 by 3 Flemion based IPMC tactile sensor array was picked out and connected to data acquisition system for voltage signal. To demonstrate the capability for vectorial force detection as well as the function of surface circuit lines, the forces with different incident angles were applied on the west segment foothill of dome, see the top scheme in Fig.8. Four cases a, b, c and d shown in Fig.8 upper graph are corresponding to horizontal, 30° to horizontal plane, 60° to horizontal plane and perpendicular to horizontal plane at summit. The signals from four channels were recorded by a USB multi-channel data acquisition device simultaneously.

The voltage signals from 4 segments are shown in Fig.9, corresponding to four cases. For loading at foothill along horizontal direction as shown in Fig.9(a), only signal from west segment show tremendous change upon stimulus. A sharp peak first appeared at the beginning to almost 0.020V, followed by sudden decay to around 0.010V in 2 seconds. Then the curve slowly decreased until another peak in minus direction upon the removal of the loading. All other three signals show no observable change during this process. For both loading cases of 30° and 60° to horizontal plane, signals from 3 segments were found to have observable change upon applied stimulus. Other than the signal from loading segment, 2 signals from north and south segments appeared as if

they were undergoing deformation to some extent as well. This might be explained by the fact that even though loading is applied at west segment, as the inclined angel increases, the loading position get more closer to the laser cut boundary pattern, see the blue circles in Fig.8 lower graph corresponding to different loading sites. As the loading position gets closer to boundary lines, the segments adjacent will be influenced and the area near the pattern will undergo some deformation, therefore smaller signals are expected to generate in this case. In the case of loading at summit, similar magnitude from 4 segments was expected. From Fig.9(d), it clearly shows that all of them show step-like curve upon stimulus with reasonably small deviation in magnitude, indicating that all segments deformed uniformly and sent out electric signals simultaneously. In addition, we observed that the magnitude of the signals at west segments in cases (b), (c) and (d) were much lower than that of case (a). Especially for the plateau stage, the magnitude of west segment signal was almost 5 times higher than the counterparts in other three cases. Here we propose that as in case (a) the signal was picked up right next to the loading position, where generated most signal during deformation. For other three cases, signals need to transfer from middle of the samples to the sides to reach the surface electrode for signal collection, and they will generally decrease due to the surface resistance of the sample. However, we definitely need to investigate into more depth about this phenomenon in future.

Fig. 8 Cross-sectional and top view of one tactile sensor dome out of 3 by 3 arrays mounted on the dome shaped PDMS substrate with four surface electrode circuit lines under the applied loading along different incident angles (shown as blue arrows)

Fig. 9 Signals simultaneously recorded under applied loading: (a) at west foothill, (b) 30° to horizontal plane, (c) 60° to horizontal plane and (d) perpendicular to horizontal plane at summit

CONCLUSION

A bio-inspired design was described and applied to build 3-D papillae dome structure for vectorial tactile sensors. Surface electrode circuit lines have been successfully done by using Dispensing System. The circuit lines were characterized and demonstrated for high conductivity. Based on the tactile sensor element with dispensed surface electrode, multi-channel signal detections have been done and the results were discussed. It exhibited good ability for vectorial force detection. Further investigation needs to be done for the factors influencing the signal magnitude.

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